

GROUND MOTION CLASSIFICATION FROM EUROPEAN GROUND MOTION SERVICE DATA USING EXTREME GRADIENT BOOSTING

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes a supervised classifier of ground motion phenomena using as main input the SAR Differential Interferometry (DInSAR) data contained in the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) datasets. The classifier operates on the active deformation areas (ADAs) extracted from the EGMS data, which are categorized into three deformation classes, i.e. deep-seated gravitational slope deformation (DSGSD), landslide and subsidence. Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Land Cover maps are used as ancillary input data, whereas landslide and subsidence inventories are employed as ground truth to form the training dataset. The implemented machine learning (ML) classifier employs the Extreme Gradient Boosting technique on a set of features extracted from the input data. Feature importance is analysed to provide an insight on the physical meaning of the implemented classification, moving towards the explainable artificial intelligence paradigm. The results show good classification performance on the test dataset. The classification reliability is evaluated on the unseen data through class probabilities.

Index Terms— *Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), SAR differential interferometry (DInSAR), ground motion classification, Extreme Gradient Boosting.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The last decades have seen a growing need for sophisticated tools to monitor ground-motion (GM) phenomena, such as landslides and subsidence, with the aim of mitigating risk for the built environment and infrastructure. Satellite-borne sensors have been widely utilised in the recent years to measure the properties of wide areas of the Earth surface in a systematic way, which includes the images recorded by SAR on-board sensors. GM phenomena have shown to be well studied using the Persistent Scatterer SAR Interferometry (PSInSAR) technique [1], that measures the displacement of strong radar reflectors, i.e. persistent scatterers (PS), on the radar line-of-sight, by processing the SAR interferometric phases. PSInSAR was employed to produce a monitoring service of GM phenomena over the European territory, the EGMS [2]. The availability of such an extended dataset allows implementing wide area tools to detect and classify GM phenomena, that can be useful for potential users (e.g. civil protection authorities) to evaluate hazard and mitigate risks. This work proposes a wide-area ground motion classifier (GMC) that categorizes areas affected by ground

deformation phenomena into three main classes, i.e. deep-seated gravitational slope deformation (DSGSD), landslides and subsidence. Active deformation areas (ADAs) are first extracted from the EGMS Basic product data, by using a previously developed tool, the ADA Finder [3][4]. The resulting European map of ADA polygons is the input of the GMC implemented. The training dataset for the GMC is obtained by matching the European ADA map with ground truth/labelling data. In this work the GMC is implemented over the territory of Italy, using the Italian National Landslide Inventory [5] to label DSGSD [6] and landslide ADAs, and the subsidence map of Emilia-Romagna region to label subsidence ADAs [7]. The classification problem that is tackled in this work can be defined as a supervised feature-based classification with a training dataset that contains missing values. In fact, we recall that the GMC dataset may contain missing values if an ADA polygon for a fixed orbit trajectory does not contain any PS point of the opposite trajectory. However, ML algorithms that have been previously employed for feature-based classification of GM activity from PSInSAR data, such as random forest [8], does not support the presence of missing values. Hence, we selected the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) technique for classification problem. XGB belongs to the ensemble learning family and is used in various ML applications, due to its good performance and versatility [9]. The contributions of this work can be summarized as (i) the development of an XGB classifier of ground deformation phenomena combining PSInSAR (EGMS) data, DEM and Land Cover map, preceded by (ii) the systematic derivation of a training dataset for such classifier using labelling data available from landslide and subsidence inventories.

2. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The EGMS distributes three levels of products: (i) Basic, consisting of line-of-sight (LOS) velocity maps in ascending and descending orbits; (ii) Calibrated, obtained by correcting the Basic product data using Global Navigation Satellite Service (GNSS) data as reference; (iii) Ortho, i.e. vertical and horizontal (East-West) displacements computed from the Calibrated data. The data refer to the period ranging from 2016 to 2022. Both Basic and Calibrated products are derived from full resolution (~4 by 14 m) Sentinel-1 radar images. The EGMS Basic product data were chosen as input data, as they are sampled at full resolution and do not contain the long-term deformation introduced by GNSS-based

calibration at the second level of EGMS products, allowing the analysis of local ground deformation phenomena. The European Digital Elevation Model (EuDEM, 30 m resolution) and its derived slope and aspect maps and the Corine Land Cover (CLC) maps are used as ancillary data in the GMC implementation. Ground truth datasets were used to label the obtained ADAs and generate the GMC training dataset. The Italian National Landslide Inventory (“Inventario dei Fenomeni Franosi in Italia”, IFFI, 1:10000 scale) [5] collects landslide events over the Italian territory, ranging from DSGSDs to rotational/translational landslides and debris flows. In this work, fast GM events, such as debris flow, are not considered, as they are not detectable by satellite PSInSAR methods. The ground truth dataset for the subsidence phenomena was generated from a dataset [6] of the subsidence areas in the Po River basin in Emilia-Romagna (Italy), an area with flat topography affected by a slow wide-area subsidence (1-2 mm/year), with faster local subsidence phenomena, both natural and anthropic.

3. PRE-PROCESSING

3.1 ADA detection

The first pre-processing step extracts the clusters of PS points associated with ADAs. European ADA maps were generated from the EGMS Basic ascending and descending datasets by applying the ADA Finder tool. These results and the ADA Finder method are described extensively in [3] and [4].

3.2 Training Dataset Preparation

The following preparation step creates a uniformized GMC dataset of ADAs from the European ADA maps. Such dataset will be the basis to train and test ML classifiers, thus for each polygon it contains geographical data and specific classification features. The creation of the GMC dataset starts from the European ADA maps for the ascending and descending LOS. The intersecting ascending/descending ADAs are merged to form one ADA of the GMC dataset (which will be referred to as global ADA), whereas the ADAs that have no intersections are directly included into the GMC dataset. The global ADAs are then labelled using the ground-truth datasets described in Section 2, and collected into the GMC training dataset, whereas the remaining ADAs are collected into the unlabelled GMC dataset (unseen data). Assigning a GM class to the unlabelled ADAs is the final objective of this work. Following the creation of the dataset, classification features are computed for each global ADA. The EGMS PS points contained within each global ADA polygon are extracted and their features computed from the PS point metrics in the EGMS dataset (i.e. velocity, acceleration, seasonality). In the case of no intersection, the global ADA polygon obtained from a single Sentinel-1 orbit is used to extract the PS points of the opposite orbit associated with that global ADA, and their metrics added to the feature vector. If the number of opposite-orbit points is smaller than an acceptable limit (set as 3), the feature values for that orbit are marked as missing values. The feature vector structure is summarized in Table 1. The features are associated with PS

data are doubled to consider the ascending and descending Sentinel-1 orbit trajectories, yielding a feature vector of 21 features. The training dataset (Fig.1) contains 15898 ADAs, and the numbers of ADAs per class are as follows: 2169 (DSGSD), 6179 (landslide), 5460 (subsidence). The cross-correlation among some selected features is analysed through the scatterplots in Fig. 2, showing that the combinations of features that better separate the three groups of samples are *Mean_DEM - Mean_Slope* (Fig.2d), *MnVelASC-Mean_DEM* (Fig.2b) and *MnVelASC-Mean_Slope* (Fig.2c).

Table 1 – Feature vector structure for the GMC

Feature Name	Description
<i>MnVel</i>	Mean velocity (PS)
<i>MnVStd</i>	Mean standard deviation of velocity (PS)
<i>MnAcc</i>	Mean acceleration (PS)
<i>MnAStd</i>	Mean standard deviation of acceleration (PS)
<i>MnSeas</i>	Mean seasonality (PS)
<i>MnDA</i>	Mean dispersion of amplitude (PS)
<i>MnTCoh</i>	Mean temporal coherence (PS)
<i>Mean_DEM</i>	Mean DEM value
<i>Std_DEM</i>	Standard deviation of DEM
<i>Mean_Slope</i>	Mean slope value
<i>Std_Slope</i>	Standard deviation of slope
<i>Mean_Aspect</i>	Mean value of the aspect angle
<i>Std_Aspect</i>	Standard deviation of the aspect angle values
<i>LandCover</i>	Dominant land cover/use class within the ADA

4. GROUND MOTION CLASSIFICATION

4.1 Method: Extreme Gradient Boosting

The GMC was implemented by the XGB algorithm [9], which is an ensemble technique that builds models sequentially, by progressively combining base learners. XGB uses decision trees as base learners and includes regularization terms to penalize the complexity of the model, avoid overfitting and ensure generalization. The XGB operation can be summarized by:

1. *Initialization*: start with a simple initial model, such as predicting the mean of the target variable.
2. *Adding trees sequentially*. Each iteration computes the pseudo-residuals, i.e. the gradients of the loss function with respect to the current predictions and fits a new tree to these residuals. The added tree should predict the gradient and thus help reduce the errors made by the current model.
3. *Learning objective and tree pruning*. XGB optimizes an objective function that combines a loss function (*softmax* for multi-class classification) and both L1 and L2 regularization terms (respectively indicated as *alpha* and *lambda*). Tree pruning is handled with the *maximum depth* (i.e. the maximum number of levels of a tree) and the *minimum child weight* (i.e. the minimum sum of instance weights of a child).
5. *Shrinkage*. After adding a new tree, XGB weights the predictions (i.e. class scores) by a shrinkage factor (*learning rate*), ensuring that subsequent trees make only small adjustments, improving model robustness.
6. *Output*. The final prediction for an instance is the sum of the initial prediction and the weighted scores of all trees. The

output scores for each class are transformed to probability values using the *softmax* function. XGB provides a measure of feature importance based on the number of times a feature is used to split the data across all the trees and the relative gain in the loss function attributed to each split. This information summarizes the impact of each feature on the ground motion classification, which is intended to introduce the concept of explainable artificial intelligence (explainable AI) in the study of GM phenomena from SAR data. The main XGB hyperparameters (*learning rate*, *min child weight*, *maximum depth*, *alpha*, *lambda*) were set by a tuning routine based on a Bayesian optimization framework [9]. The hyperparameter tuning launched 100 iterations, employing the accuracy as optimization metric, resulting in the following optimal hyperparameter values: *learning_rate* = 0.089, *max_depth* = 8, *min_child_weight* = 0, *alpha* = 0, *lambda* = 0.787.

Fig. 1 Map of the GMC training dataset (Italy)

Fig. 2 Scatterplots of the main GMC features

4.2 Results – Test Dataset

The GMC classifier was implemented on the training dataset, which was split into a training (70%) and a test (30%) set. The results are computed on the test set evaluating the confusion matrix (Table 2) and the classification metrics (Table 3). Fig. 3 shows the values of the GMC feature importance (I_F). The most important features are the mean slope ($I_F \sim 45\%$) and mean DEM ($I_F \sim 25\%$). The features resulting from PSInSAR processing have I_F values smaller than 5%. However, the total importance of the PSInSAR-derived features is approximately equal to 25%. The results highlight that the subsidence class gives the best classification results. The subsidence phenomenon presents unique properties compared to landslides and DSGSD, as it occurs mainly in flat topography areas, such as plains and coastal environments, and has strong vertical ground deformation component. This leads to high accuracy value for the subsidence class and to the high importance values of the slope and DEM features. On the other hand, landslide and DSGSD classes have similar characteristics (occurring in areas with non-flat topography, i.e. mountainous and hilly environments) and they are often spatially close, as DSGSD are likely to evolve into landslides. This results in lower accuracy values for both classes and higher number of false positives. Table 4 shows the classification metrics if only the ancillary data are used (i.e. no PSInSAR data included), showing a performance decrease, particularly for the DSGSD class.

4.3 Results – Unseen Data

The GMC was applied to the unseen dataset, which collects the unlabelled ADAs, yielding a new map of classified ADAs (Fig. 4): 5706 for the DSGSD class, 72319 for the landslide class and 21863 for the subsidence class. As introduced in Section 4.1, the GMC assigns probability values for each class. We studied the distribution of these probability values (normalized histograms in Fig.5) to evaluate the reliability of the classification. The probability values for each GMC class are all exponentially distributed, thus the performed classification seems to be quite reliable from this analysis.

Table 2 Confusion matrix –ground truth (rows), predicted (columns)

	DSGSD	Landslide	Subsidence
DSGSD	462	82	0
Landslide	205	1770	2
Subsidence	1	1	1620

Table 3 – Performance metrics –GMC

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
DSGSD	0.69	0.85	0.76	544
Landslide	0.96	0.90	0.92	1977
Subsidence	0.99	0.99	0.99	1622

Table 4 – Performance metrics – GMC on ancillary data

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
DSGSD	0.65	0.46	0.54	544
Landslide	0.82	0.90	0.86	1977
Subsidence	0.99	0.99	0.99	1622

Fig. 3 Feature importance values of the implemented GMC.

The subsidence class is the best performing one (its distribution has the highest exponential degree), followed by the landslide and DSGSD ones. The map of classified ADAs shows high concentration of subsidence ADAs in the main flat topography areas of the Italian territory, i.e. the basins of the Po, Adige and Arno rivers, and the plains of Apulia and Campania regions. Coastal subsidence can also be noticed. DSGSD ADAs are mainly located in areas with high slopes and altitudes, i.e. the Alpine arc and the Apennine Mountains. Most ADAs were labelled as landslides, which can be justified by the fact that this class includes phenomena of different nature.

5. FUTURE WORK

Future work will be focused on classifying deformation subclasses. For instance, the subsidence class could be split into mining-induced deformation, subsidence due to ground-water exploitation, underground gas storage, and others.

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REFERENCES

[1] A.Ferretti, C.Prati, F.Rocca, Permanent scatterers in SAR interferometry, *IEEE Trans. on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 39(1), 8-20, 2001.

[2] M.Crosetto, L.Solari, M. Mróz, *et al.* (2020). The evolution of wide-area DInSAR: From regional and national services to the European Ground Motion Service, *Remote Sensing*, 12(12).

[3] A.Barra, L.Solari, M.Béjar-Pizarro, *et al.* A methodology to detect and update active deformation areas based on Sentinel-1 SAR images, *Remote Sensing*, 9, 1002, 2017.

[4] R. Palamà, M.Cuevas-González, A.Barra *et al.*, Automatic Ground Deformation Detection from European Ground Motion Service Products, *2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS 2023)*, Pasadena, CA, USA, 2023.

[5] A.Trigila, *et al.*, Quality assessment of the Italian Landslide Inventory using GIS processing. *Landslides*, 7, 455–470,2010.

[6] F.Dramis, M.Sorriso-Valvo, Deep-seated gravitational slope deformations, related landslides and tectonics, *Engineering Geology*, Vol. 38, Issues 3–4, pp 231-243, 1994

[7] G. Bitelli, F. Bonsignore, I. Pellegrino, L. Vittuari. (2015), Evolution of the techniques for subsidence monitoring at regional scale: the case of Emilia-Romagna region, (Italy). Proceedings of the Ninth International Symposium on Land Subsidence, Nagoya (Japan), November 15-19, IAHS, 92, 1-7

[8] D. Festa, N. Casagli, F. Casu, *et al.* (2022) Automated classification of A-DInSAR-based ground deformation by using random forest, *GIScience & Remote Sensing*, 59:1, 1749-1766.

[9] T.Chen, C. Guestrin, (2016). XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System. In Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD '16). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.02754>

[10] B.Shahriari, K.Swersky, Z.Wang, R.P.Adams, N.de Freitas, (2016). Taking the Human Out of the Loop: A Review of Bayesian Optimization. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 104(1), 148–175

Fig. 4 Map of the classified ADA from the unseen data (Italy).

Fig. 5 Distribution (normalized histogram) of the probability values for each predicted GMC class